

Standard Operating Procedure	Version: 2
Culture and identification of ESBL <i>E. coli</i> and ESBL <i>K. pneumoniae</i> on Chromogenic Agar.	
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Version History

Version	Date	Comment
1.0	01/04/19	Initial version
2.0	01/07/19	Changes after initial pilot phase

1. Introduction

This method is applicable for the culture of ESBL *E. coli* (ESBL -E) and ESBL *K. pneumoniae* (ESBL-K) from stool (human / animal) and environmental samples obtained from households included in the DRUM study.

The proportion of patients admitted to hospitals in Uganda and Malawi with invasive infections caused by ESBL resistant Enterobacteriaceae including ESBL-E and ESBL-K is increasing. Given the reduced availability of Carbapenems, many of these drug-resistant infections are locally untreatable. To understand the drivers of this antimicrobial resistance, further evidence of the role of household environment contamination on human and animal carriage with ESBL-E and ESBL-K is required.

2. Purpose

Chromogenic agar will be used to culture ESBL *E. coli* / *K. pneumoniae* isolates, and speciation will be identified in conjunction with PCR results.

3. Responsibilities

- Field workers
 - Collection of human and animal stool, and environmental samples in according to Sample Collection SOPs
 - Correct labelling of collection samples
 - Prompt transport of collected samples to the laboratory
 - Completion of sample collection log
- Study Laboratory Technicians
 - Register samples on DRUM teleform /eLIMS system
 - Ensure prompt collection of study samples from laboratory reception
 - Double-check correct sample labelling
 - Processing ESBL positive samples in accordance with this SOP
 - Storage of samples for further analysis in accordance with this SOP
- Principal Investigators
 - Ensure laboratory training in sample processing procedures provided
 - Undertake quality control checks of laboratory processing.

4. Procedure

4.1 Materials needed

ChromAGAR ESBL agar plate
Sterile 1ul & 10ul Bacterial loops
Microbank storage vial with beads
1.8ml cryovials (premade with BPW/Glycerol)
Spot Indole Reagent
Whatman No. 1 filter paper
Gloves
Fine marker

4.2 Storage conditions

All reagents should be stored as per the instructions of the manufacturer

4.3. Test Procedure – Culture preparation

1. For each sample tested, obtain the original BPW samples from the incubator.
2. Using a chromogenic agar plate, create a half streak plate using a 1µl microbiological loop of the incubated BPW (using 1 plate for 2 samples)
3. Incubate the chromogenic agar plate in an aerobic incubator at 37°C for 18-24 hours.
4. Discard the remaining BPW (ensuring that 1.8ml has been stored in a cryovial first – as per SOP1/2).

4.4 Test Procedure – Speciation and selection

1. Read chromogenic agar plate after 18-24 hours. ANY growth is a potential ESBL producer.
2. Speciate as table below. Store single colony pick of each of the following in a microbank vial at -80°C.

- a. Pink colony (x1)
 - b. White - indole positive colony (x1)
 - c. Blue colony (x1)
3. For blue colonies confirm *K. pneumoniae* speciation with HRM PCR.
 4. If a mixed plate is obtained, as above, store a single colony each of ESBL-E (pink), ESBL-E (white) and blue (ESBL-K vs alternate) in microbank vials, making a total of 3 colonies.

Appearance*	Organism*	Action
Dark pink to reddish 	ESBL <i>E. coli</i>	Speciation on chromogenic agar is sufficient. Take a single colony pick and store isolate in microbank storage vial at -80°C <i>In all plates where there is growth of pink, blue or white colonies, once ID has been confirmed and colonies stored, a plate sweep should be taken.</i>
Metallic blue (+/- reddish halo) 	ESBL KEC (Klebsiella, Enterobacter, Citrobacter)	Store 1x blue colony per plate (prior to waiting for the speciation results). Speciation on ChromAgar is insufficient. Confirm blue colony speciation via HRM PCR. 1) Take ¼ - ½ of a colony and run melt curve PCR. 2) Take the other half of the colony and store on microbank storage vial at -80°C. <i>In all plates where there is growth of pink, blue or white colonies, once ID has been confirmed and colonies stored, a plate sweep should be taken.</i>

<p>Brown halo b)</p> <p>This plate shows blue colonies (Klebsiella) and Proteus with brown halo</p>	<p>ESBL Proteus</p>	<p>Document findings and no further processing</p>
<p>Cream/White</p>	<p>ESBL Acinetobacter Possible E. coli</p>	<p>Test ½ of a white colony with Indole (method below)</p> <p>Then, if INDOLE POSITIVE, store the other ½ of the same 1x white colony in microbank vial as presumed E coli.</p>
<p>Translucent, (+/- natural pigmentation cream to green)</p>	<p>ESBL Pseudomonas</p>	<p>Document findings and no further processing</p>
<p>Colourless</p>	<p>Stenotrophomonas</p>	<p>Document findings and no further processing</p>
<p>Gram(+) strains → inhibited</p>		
<p>Non Resistant Other Gram(-) strains → inhibited</p>		
<p>Yeasts → mostly inhibited</p>		

* Pictures and organism ID taken from CHROMAgar™ ESBL NT-EXT-034 V5.0 / 08-Aug-16

- For plates where there is ANY growth (white, blue, pick colonies), also undertake a plate sweep after the *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* colonies have been placed in microvials.

6. Ensure documentation of results is noted on DRUM teleform/LIMS system and discard plates after speciation, plate sweep and storage.

4.5. Test Procedure – Indole Testing

Spot Indole Reagent

Whatman No. 1 filter paper

1x 10ul bacterial loop

1. Using Filter Paper

- a. Dispense 1-2 drops of Spot Indole Reagent onto a piece of filter paper (Whatman No. 1 or equivalent).
- b. Using an inoculating loop, smear the growth from an actively growing white culture from Chromogenic Agar onto the reagent saturated area of the filter paper.
- c. Observe the filter paper for the development of a blue colour within 3 minutes.

2. Interpretation of Results

- **Positive Reaction**- The development of a blue colour within 3 minutes
 - In this case, the sample should be stored in a microvial.
 - Document results on the DRUM teleform/LIMS system
- **Negative reaction**- The development of a pink colour within 3 minutes.
 - In this case, the colony is unlikely to be *E. coli* and is therefore discarded.
 - Document results on the DRUM teleform/LIMS system

4.6 Test Procedure – Microbank Inoculation

1. Label a separate microbank vial corresponding to the correct number in the database for each organism to be stored (*E. coli (pink)*, *E. coli (white)* and *K. pneumoniae*).
2. Using aseptic technique, unscrew the microbank vial.
3. Using a sterile inoculating loop pick off a single colony from the ESBL ChromAgar plates and place into the microbank vial.
4. Using aseptic technique, replace the cap on the microbank vial tightly, and invert it 4-5 times to emulsify the organism. Do not vortex.
5. Let the microbank vial sit for 2 minutes to allow the isolate to bind to the beads. Remove the cap and use a sterile disposable Pasteur pipette to remove the cryo-preserved. The beads should now be as free of liquid as possible.
6. Close the microbank vial (finger tight only). It is important that they are not overtightened.
7. Place the microbank vial in a Microbank storage box and freeze at -80°C.

4.7 Test Procedure – Plate Sweep

1. Take a 10µl loop and streak across the plate left to right and up / down, across the *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* isolates picking up multiple colonies.
2. If there is more than one colony colour of morphology, make sure that you pick up one of each type.
3. Then place this loop into a cryovial with BPW and glycerol, and store in the -80°C.

4.8 Test Procedure – Creation of cryovial for storage of plate sweep.

1. Prepare a freeze matrix, and aliquot into sterile cryovials.
2. Use (autoclaved) BPW and glycerol (50% BPW: Glycerol)
3. The glycerol is heavy so mix well when working.
4. Aseptically add 1ml of the mix to cryovials and store at 4°C

To subculture from frozen stock, stab a hot loop into the vial while keeping the sample as cold as possible. Streak the inoculum to the appropriate plate medium, and immediately re-freeze the vial. Freeze thaw cycles decrease the viability of the bacteria. Complete thawing of the sample may require new preparation from fresh subculture.

5. Quality Control

The following Quality control will be undertaken for ESBL culture/plate creation:

- ESBL CHROMagar™ plates will be made in batches each week, using the manufacturer set standards and guidance.
- Newly poured plates should be left on the bench overnight at room temperature and checked the following morning for the presence of contamination.
- For each batch of ESBL plates made, 3 plates should be tested with a positive and negative control for ESBL-E (using the same microbiological processing methods used for other samples).
 - The positive control to be used is an in-house confirmed ESBL *K. pneumoniae* (obtained from MLW laboratory in Malawi, or IDI in Uganda).
 - The negative control to be used is an in-house confirmed non-ESBL *Salmonella enterica* (obtained from MLW laboratory in Malawi, or IDI in Uganda).
- Once quality checks have been completed, the plates can be stored in the cold room (maintaining 2-8°C) until use, and not kept for longer than 14 days.
- If any plates (i.e. contamination on morning review) or batches (i.e. positive/negative control failure) do not pass quality checks, they are to be discarded.
 - For controls, if failed, discard the whole batch
 - For contamination, discard individual plates

6. Health and Safety

Please refer to risk assessment tools and local health and safety guidelines